

IMPROVING RELATIONS ON THE ABOLITION OF MARRIAGE IN UZBEKISTAN (ON THE EXAMPLE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES)

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the author describes the procedure for canceling marriage in Uzbekistan and foreign provides information on the experience of states. Deficiencies in the legal system and he presented them with suggestions and Ficks. What causes a divorce in the world cases are given as an example. Women's Committee Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan he outlined his arguments on the questionnaire conducted by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On the percentage indicator on the construction and termination of marriage in our country touched on the basics.

Duality in the regulation of property relations of spouses in the current period there are: a number of states are characteristic of the rule of the Earth in family law, in most countries, the fact that until the present period in the family is not equal to the couple preserved. Marriage contract under the Civil Code in these states established, the contract is concluded before marriage, in which, first of all, the property of the wife the right of the relative land is strengthened. As we all know, now the number of divorces in the whole world is Seconds it is increasing every year. This figure is up in Europe. Islamic only in countries, the family has been preserved for many years as an almost indestructible structure coming. Often it is only a man's right to break the bonds of marriage there the presence is seen as a cause. A woman, on the other hand, has the right to appeal only to the court. It is regarded in itself as a subordinate act condemned in society. This and in order to issue a finding application, serious reasons must be cited. Many and the human rights laws that apply in countries are valid in arab countries it remains not to be done.

Several developed and developing countries of Europe-France, The number of divorces in Germany, Russia and the United States is increasing every year compared to the number of marriages. But according to sociologist experts, in these countries a quarter of divorces happen due to treason. Also the population increase in well-being, material wealth among all layers of society fair distribution, rapid development of the country's economic system, population provision of the rules of law and increasing the rights of women in recent years the course of *Paradox2* has the opposite effect as. Economic of European countries how each of the spouses feels safe in their developed country, the fact that he is alone ready for all difficulties and situations, and even with children this situation has led to a sense of

confidence to be able to get out of several that will cause the dissolution of marriage in European countries there are factors that include:

- *Betrayal and feeling alien;*
- *Various infectious diseases (HIV and AIDS);*
- *Alcohol and drug addiction (Europe on the consumption of alcohol products the leaders of the countries of Moldova and Lithuania (while the Republic of Uzbekistan alcohol products are ranked 138th in terms of istemoli), Russian alcohol one of the leading countries in Europe for the supply of drinks used;*
- *Homosexual relationships (emergence of new whistleblowers) infertility or unwillingness to have children;*
- *Dependence on computer games (In European countries in the last 10 years addiction to computer games causes the issue of marriage to be reversed is happening).*

Family-legal relations in the country lasting legal relations enters the order. This relationship is with the objectives of the legal relationship it is carried out in a close manner. The purpose of starting a family (marriage) is the couple's based on his agreement, he aims to live together for the rest of his life. Unfortunately, in society there are many cases between families, the consequence of which is the main one for the termination of marriage there will be one of the reasons. As a result, the conditions under which the marriage was concluded for a lifetime are violated.

We can witness the termination of the marriage at every step. In our country the reforms carried out in recent years and the attention given to women's rights of great importance. Young marriage of girls (being a bride) of the divorces the fact that it is causing an increase is the same fact. Indeed, according to the women's committee, there are 7 million families in Uzbekistan.6 young families, mostly everyday quarrels, that is, parting due to financial problems. Women's 17-18 young people get married in a questionnaire conducted by the committee ready? - to the question asked, 75% of participants are both (female and male) ready they argued that it was not. 8% of participants can only be female or male ready it is believed that. Approximately equal numbers of participants found it difficult to answer (8%), while 9% of respondents believed that both were ready to get married. At this point, the question arises: the age of starting a family according to the current law is 17-18 make up the age, increase the age of marriage to prevent divorces is it reasonable? To this question, I have both positive and negative arguments:

Argument 1. In my opinion, changing the age of marriage cannot prevent a divorce, the effect of unemployment on the origin of the findings is also great. Young people with work in order to ensure and make them a representative of a particular industry, earn them allows.

Argument 2. The age of family building of foreign countries, that is, on average 23-25 years old if we include marriage in our legislation, the demographic in our country affects the growth rate, which can lead to a decrease in fertility.

This situation is due to the fact that there is no possible shortage of products and we will have saved our natural resources (resources) for our future generations. The highest rates of marriage in our country at the junction of Regions if we dwell on the stage of "promille " 8 of this indicator review on let's go out:

Khorezm (6,4), Karakalpakstan(5,2), Syrdarya (5,1) and Surkhandarya (4,9) recorded in the regions. The lowest coefficient is Namangan (3,6), Samarkand (3,7), Navoi (3,8) and Jizzakh (4,2) regions are noted. First half in Uzbekistan 75.5 thousand marriages and 12.8 thousand divorces were recorded in the anniversary, this is the same as last year 27,5 percent and 20 percent less, respectively, compared to the period. 19.6 of broken families the percentage (about 2,500) has two or more children. And the highest divorces for half a year in the section of regions are Tashkent (1,3), It was observed in Syrdarya (1,2), Andijan (1,0) and Navoi (0,9) regions. Lowest the indicator is Karakalpakstan (0,5), Kashkadarya (0,5), Khorezm (0,5) and Surkhandarya (0,6) recorded in the provinces.¹⁰

As a result of the reforms carried out by our government, the standard of living of the population of our country is improved, in addition to the benefits reduced ground is being created. According to Article 37 of the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan termination of marriage is

- *Carried out on the following grounds:*
- *Death of one of the spouses;*
- *Announcement of the death of one of the missing husband or wife in court order;*
- *By divorce in accordance with the application of one of the spouses or both;*

The court issued a guardian of a husband or wife who was deemed incapable of circulation in accordance with the application, the termination of the marriage relationship is established. The listed facts are the grounds for the termination of marriage. Divorce from marriage it happens only in the life of a couple, differing from the two bases presented above.

Death is a legal fact that ends the marriage relationship between the couple. It is their own to declare one of the spouses died based on the decision of the court it is equated to death by legal consequence. Therefore found dead the marriage between the person and his husband or wife is also completed. In our society marriage is a union concluded together. In certain cases, if the family is practically broken in case of divorce, it may have been terminated on the basis of divorce. Divorce couple from marriage the legal relationship between the future will be the basis for the passage of time. Such divorce is different from finding a marriage invalid.

For example, the right of one of the ex-spouses to receive alimony is preserved in this case remains. The grounds for separation from marriage are determined differently in different countries, foreign some in the solution of separation relations from marriage complicated by the element causes problems. In particular, to decide on the basis of the material legislation of which country is not allowed to separate from marriage; spouses are different how to behave when belonging to citizenship; What are the rules of mass order application in cases. Spouses who have different citizenship or have one citizenship separation of foreign citizens from marriage having not only the collusion of the choice of law, what is the case of separation from marriage, which is important not only with the problem it will also be associated with a procedural problem that determines the belonging of the country to the court.

And in this-Articles 28, 29 of the Minsk convention of 1993 from marriage in determining which country the case applies to the jurisdiction in matters of separation they proceed from the following situations:

- *In view of the work on separation from marriage, the citizenship of the spouses is in the form of the institutions of the country are representative;*
- *If at the time of applying for an application, both of the spouses are in a different country institutions of this country to see the case of separation from marriage if they live in the territory they are also competent. That is, that the spouses also apply to the court of this country can;*
- *If the spouses are citizens of different countries, the case of separation from marriage is authorized to be seen by the institutions of the country where both spouses live;*

Separation from marriage if spouses live on the territory of different countries work to see the institutions of both countries where couples live authorized.

Conclusion: one of the highest values in the Republic of Uzbekistan is Human rights and freedoms promulgated in the Constitution are considered complete. The same together with the obligation to recognize, comply with and protect them of the state imposed on itself, it complies with international standards in this area. To this day on arrival, civil and family rights of citizens in the Republic of Uzbekistan sufficiently effective work is being carried out in implementation and protection, and this is a powerful mechanism is created on the road. But civil and family relations if it takes on a complex nature with foreign (foreign) elements in legal terms, this only internal means are enough to protect the rights of participants international interaction with the competent authorities of foreign (foreign) states the need to establish contract-based cooperation arises. Such in cases where the effectiveness of the protection of the rights of citizens depends on the consistency of the wishes of states, on the clear regulation of their cooperation internationally, to timely introduce the norms of international law into national legislation, the state it is carried out in such a way as to create a system of bodies.

Civil status according to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in cases where divorce from marriage is possible in the bodies of writing acts divorce from such marriage is in the diplomatic missions of the Republic of Uzbekistan or it can be done in consular institutions. But the consulate separation from marriage, in contrast to the registration of marriage in their institution, can also be carried out between persons for whom one is a foreign citizen. In a foreign country relations of separation of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan from marriage it can also be carried out in the competent authorities of this country. Recognition of court decisions on separation from Marriage issued in Uzbekistan in foreign countries means that this decision is equated with decisions made in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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